

Controlled synthesis of CuO box shaped nanoparticles and their application in nitrophenol reduction

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Manuscript received 31 December 2009, accepted 25 February 2010

Abstract : Box shaped copper(II) oxide particles with an average diameter of ~100 nm were synthesized by warming $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ in cyclodextrin at ~80–90 °C. The tunable size, gram level preparation and characterization of the single crystalline CuO nanoboxes were demonstrated. The procedure involves the use of common copper compounds as precursor and unmodified cyclodextrin as capping agent for box shaped nanoparticles. The optical absorption spectrum provides a band gap of 3.05 eV for the prepared CuO nanoparticles. A possible mechanism that accounts the growth of these nanostructures has been described. The synthesized CuO nanoparticles were exploited as catalyst for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol.

Keywords : CuO NP, cyclodextrin, catalysis, 4-nitrophenol.

Introduction

Over the past years a significant amount of research activities in the chemical community have been directed towards the development of new technologies and methodologies for the synthesis of nanoparticles using environmentally benign processes. This area of chemistry has received extensive attention and is often referred to 'green chemistry'.¹ Nanoparticles with various size and shape find technological applications in areas such as ceramics, magnetic recording, semiconductors and metallic catalysts because of their novel mechanical, electronic, magnetic and optical properties compared to those of conventional bulk materials^{2–6}. To date, nanocrystals with a wealth of shapes have been produced, which can be broadly classified by their dimensionalities : zero-dimensional (0D) spheres, cubes, decahedrons, icosahedrons, and octahedrons, one-dimensional (1D) nanorods and wires, two-dimensional (2D) nanodisks, plates and other elaborated shapes such as rod-based multipods and nanostars^{7–15}. Because the properties of materials at the nanoscale are strongly influenced by their shape and dimensional constraint¹⁶, it is expected that the synthesis of nanostructured materials, particularly those with structures such as nanocubes, nanoboxes,

nanospheres etc., could enhance their intrinsic characteristics for use in existing applications^{14,15,17}.

Due to the limited availability of precious metals, attention has been directed to the base metal oxides and transition metal oxides. Hence, nanobuilding blocks of transition metal oxides have now been prepared by various processes^{18–20}. These are sonochemical method, sol-gel technique one-step solid state reaction method at room temperature, electrochemical method, thermal decomposition of precursors and co-implantation of metal and oxygen ions and so on^{21–25}. The possibility of constituting a nanotoolbox for a "bottom-up" approach in nanoscience and nanotechnology is of immense importance. Metal oxide nanoparticles have a large surface area and this gives nanomaterials great advantages over conventional materials in many applications, such as high-critical-temperature superconductors, heterogeneous catalysts, complex magnetic phases and lithium-metal oxide electrochemical cells^{26–30}. Among these transition metal oxides, cupric oxide (CuO) has been extensively studied due to its important catalytic properties and innumerable other applications. CuO (the common phase of copper oxide), in particular, is a *p*-type semiconducting material (energy gap of ~1.4 eV) that exhibits

photoconductive, field emission and photovoltaic properties^{31–33}. Though some of the methods have been suggested for the preparation of CuO nanoparticles a technique to produce small but tunable oxide nanoparticles with a narrow size distribution in an organic host is still lacking. Geckeler *et al.*¹ has reported the synthesis of CuO nanoparticle using β -CD by calcination in the furnace at 500 °C for 1 h. Thus, there remains a challenge to a find convenient, mild, simple and green pathway to produce CuO nanoparticles by using a suitable macrocyclic organic host and environmentally benign solvent. Water is particularly attractive because it is environmentally benign and inexpensive. In this communication, we focus on the synthesis of CuO nanoparticles via a green pathway using cyclodextrins (CDs) as a capping agent and a wonderful organic receptors^{1,34}.

Modification of CuO nanoparticle surfaces with different organic receptors is important for the development of biological traces as well as optoelectronic nanodevices. Molecules like CD, a soluble nontoxic molecule has been considered as one of the important receptors and becomes an obvious choice as it can form both channel and cage complexes incorporating nanosize metal guests with its cyclic oligosaccharide containing internal cavities. CD molecules could be employed to bring metal complexes together in close proximity to construct supramolecular structures through capping without the requirement of their covalent linkage i.e. they do not function as a ligand. Adduct formation with guest molecules in aqueous solutions is one of the most remarkable properties of CD molecules. Furthermore, depending on the relative sizes of guest and CD molecules, more than one guest can be accommodated in the cavity^{35,36}, whereas if the guest molecule is long enough, one or two CDs may be threaded along its length. The host molecules are made up of six, seven and eight glucose units connected in a large ring, called α -, β - or γ -CD respectively. We have recently reported the reducing as well as capping property of unmodified β -CD to prepare size and shape selective mono- and bimetallic metal nanoparticles in alkaline medium³⁷. With this idea in mind, for the first time we have employed unmodified CDs for the synthesis of CuO nanoparticles in aqueous solution which acts as a

stabilizing agent in alkaline medium. Finally, the CuO nanoparticles have been productively exploited as a catalyst for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) to 4-aminophenol (4-AP) in presence of NaBH_4 . The kinetic aspect of the reduction of 4-nitrophenol was studied under the experimental condition. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of synthesis of CuO particles in the nano dimension using unmodified β -CD in alkaline medium and their catalytic application for nitrophenol reduction.

This article reports a kinetic strategy to obtain exclusively box shaped stable and well-dispersed CuO particles in the nanoregime with average diameter of 100 nm via a green chemistry approach. Gram level synthesis of CuO nanoparticles was possible employing this synthetic protocol. The structure and composition of the CuO nanoparticles were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transformer infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Raman study, UV-Visible spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering (DLS). Finally, the box shaped CuO nanoparticles have been employed as catalyst in nitrophenol reduction reaction.

Results and discussion

The synthesized CuO nanoparticle was characterized using different physical techniques such as XRD, FTIR, FESEM, XPS, UV etc. studies.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of CuO nanoparticles using a target of $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) after repeated washing the synthesized particles with water. Inset shows the FTIR spectrum of the synthesized CuO nanoboxes.

Fig. 2. FESEM image low resolution (a), and high resolution with markings of length, breadth and height (b) of CuO nanoboxes. Conditions : [β -CD] = 0.0396 g in 5 ml water, [$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CuCl}_2/\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$] = 0.1 M and [NaOH] = 1.0 M.

The structure and the phase of the prepared CuO nanostructure material was obtained using XRD pattern. Fig. 1 shows the typical thin film X-ray diffraction result of the CuO nanoparticles. One crucial peak at 2θ value 32.4° communicates the (110) plane. Other two intense peaks are observed at 2θ values 35.4° and 38.5° which correspond to the (11-1) and (111 and 200) crystal planes of CuO nanoparticles. These three peaks are the characteristics of CuO. The other observed peaks are less intense and hence insignificant. The 2θ values are at 48.5° , 53.5° , 57.5° , 61.2° and 66° which corresponds to (20-2), (020), (202), (11-3) and (31-1) crystal planes respectively (JCPDS Card No. 80-1916)³⁸. The lattice constants found from JCPDS are a (\AA) : 4.6927, b (\AA) : 3.4283, c (\AA) : 5.1370, α : 90.0° , β : 99.5460° , γ : 90.0°

which are in good agreement with the standard values. $a = 4.6837 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.4226 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.1288 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 99.54^\circ$ and $\gamma = 90^\circ$. The major peaks are located at 2θ values of $20\text{--}70^\circ$ clearly indicate that the CuO product exhibits a pure phase. The XRD pattern shows that the prepared product is pure monoclinic CuO, without any trace of Cu, Cu_2O and even $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ being present.

The inset in Fig. 1 shows the FTIR spectrum of the CuO nanoparticles. The high frequency mode at about 582 cm^{-1} is reported due to Cu–O stretching vibration. Moreover, the infrared active mode of Cu_2O at 610 cm^{-1} are not observed. This further supports that the prepared nanoparticles comprise of purely CuO phase.

The morphology of the product was examined by FESEM observation. Figs. 2a and b depicts the shape and morphology of CuO nanoparticles. Fig. 2a shows that all the particles are monodispersed and exclusively box shaped. One interesting observation is that all the three CDs produced CuO nanoparticles of similar shape and morphology i.e. all the particles are box shaped. Thus similar but controlled capping action of the CDs is understandable. The FESEM image of CuO nanostructures accounts the average particle size of $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$ size range. A high resolution FESEM image of a single CuO box shaped particles is shown in Fig. 2b which shows the length, breadth and the height of a particle.

EDAX measurement indicates that the organization of the particles or the presence of the metals employed in the preparation procedure. EDAX analysis of the box shaped particles confirms the monoclinic identity of the box shaped CuO nanoparticles. In addition, the EDAX results show that the resultant powder contains strong peaks due to copper and oxygen with a Cu : O elemental ratio of unity as expected by stoichiometry and the absence of peaks due to Cu, Cu_2O and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, which corroborates with the powder XRD pattern. EDAX and XRD analysis confirms that the box shaped nanoparticles prepared using this technique are in only one phase, namely, CuO.

The structure and crystallinity of the CuO nanoparticles were further characterized using TEM analysis. Fig. 3a shows typical TEM images of the CuO nanoboxes with

Fig. 3. TEM image (a), HRTEM image (b), SAED pattern (c) and fringe spacing values (d) of CuO nanoboxes. Conditions : $[\beta\text{-CD}] = 0.0396 \text{ g in } 5 \text{ ml water}$, $[\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CuCl}_2/\text{Cu}(\text{OAC})_2] = 0.1 \text{ M}$ and $[\text{NaOH}] = 1.0 \text{ M}$.

an average diameter of $\sim 110 \text{ nm}$. Fig. 3a indicates that the sample is composed of a large quantity of box shaped particles. The image also reveals that the surface of every particle is attached with many smaller particles. A HRTEM image of edge area of one CuO nanoboxes is shown in Fig. 3b which provides strong support for the box shaped particles. The HRTEM image from one of the part of a particle shows the detail texture of the particles, which reveals that the particles are built up from different box shaped particles with an average diameter of $\sim 20 \text{ nm}$. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern on a single particle is shown in Fig. 3c. The SAED pattern shows the bright single crystalline sharp spots corresponding to the diffraction of (110), (200), (20-2), (11-3) and (31-1) planes of CuO. So from the SAED pattern it can be concluded that the particles are consistent with monoclinic structure of CuO and in pure phase. The interfringe distance is measured to be 2.8 and 2.4 \AA , which corresponds to the (110) and (11-1) planes of monoclinic CuO, agreed well with the XRD analysis (Fig. 3d).

The surfaces of the synthesized CuO particles were examined by XPS analysis. Fig. 4a shows the wide X-ray photoelectron spectrum of the prepared CuO nanoboxes. The peak at 932.23 eV , (Fig. 4b) corresponds to the binding energy of $\text{Cu}2p_{3/2}$, is in good agreement with the data observed for CuO³⁹. Fig. 4c indicates the binding energy of O_{1s} at 529.5 eV , is in well accordance with the reported value⁴¹. The peak of O^{2-} at a lower energy of 529.5 eV , is in agreement with O^{2-} in CuO. The reference peak was corrected to C_{1s} (288.6 eV). Thus, the XPS results prove that the sample is composed of CuO only.

The well-built authentication for the formation of CuO nanoboxes comes from Raman studies. The structural formation of CuO nanoboxes was studied by Raman spectroscopy. Cupric oxide (CuO) belongs to the C_{2h}^6 space group^{33,40} with two molecules per primitive cell. One can find for the zone center normal modes

$$\Gamma \equiv 4A_u + 5B_u + A_g + 2B_g$$

There are three acoustic modes ($A_u + 2B_u$), six infrared

Fig. 4. Wide X-ray photoelectron spectrum of the prepared CuO nanoboxes (a) and high resolution XPS spectra of $\text{Cu}_{2p_{3/2}}$ (b) and O_{1s} (c) using Mg as the exciting source.

active modes ($3A_u + 3B_u$), and three Raman active modes ($A_g + 2B_g$). Fig. 5 shows the three Raman active modes of CuO nanoboxes. We can assign the peak at 282 cm^{-1} to the A_g mode and the peaks at 326 and 615 cm^{-1} to the B_g modes. In Raman spectrum the second one (326 cm^{-1}) is being weakest and the third one (615 cm^{-1}) being quite broad. In comparison with the Raman vibrational spectrum of a CuO single crystal⁴⁰, the Raman peaks of the CuO nanoboxes are broadened and shifted toward high wavenumbers due to the quite higher size effects of the CuO nanoboxes.

In order to resolve the interband or excitonic transitions of CuO particles we have carried out the UV-Visible absorption measurement of CuO nanoparticles. The colloidal solution of CuO particles from any one of the CDs shows a blackish yellow color with a broad peak which is shown in Fig. 6a. Fig. 6a shows absorption maxima at $\sim 284\text{ nm}$, 278 nm and 274 nm for α -, β - and γ -CD, respectively. Out of the three CDs, γ -CD shows

Fig. 5. Raman spectrum of CuO nanoboxes. Conditions : $[\beta\text{-CD}] = 0.0396\text{ g}$ in 5 ml water, $[\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CuCl}_2/\text{Cu}(\text{OAC})_2] = 0.1\text{ M}$ and $[\text{NaOH}] = 1.0\text{ M}$.

maximum blue shifted absorption maximum which corresponds to the smaller size of the CuO particles. An estimate of the optical band gap using the absorption maximum ($\sim 278\text{ nm}$) for β -CD has been given for a semiconductor via the following equation :

$$\alpha E_p = K(E_p - E_g)^{1/2}$$

where, α is the absorption coefficient, K is a constant, E_p is the discrete photo energy and E_g is the band gap energy, a classical Tauc approach is further employed to estimate the E_g value of CuO nanoparticles^{41,42}. The plot of $(\alpha E_p)^2$ versus E_p based on the direct transition is shown in Fig. 6b. The extrapolated value (the straight lines to the X-axis) of E_p at $\alpha = 0$ gives absorption edge energies corresponding to $E_g = 3.05$ eV. This value is quite large than the value for bulk CuO (1.85 eV). The increase in the band gap of the CuO nanoparticles is indicative of quantum confinement effects arising from the box shape of the particles.

Among the three CDs, β -CD is the most widely used due to its ease of availability and internal cavity diameter that ranges from 6 to 6.5 Å. The 'mod of fit' between host and guest and the hydrophobic effects are probably the most important³⁵⁻³⁷. That is why variable concentrations of β -CD have been used for the formation of CuO nanoparticles. It functions as a capping agent but

not as a ligand. It may be mentioned that all capping agents may not serve as ligand as this case of β -CD may be. For the lowest concentration of β -CD (1 mM), it shows red shifted absorption maximum (~280 nm) and with the highest concentration (10 mM) an absorption maximum at ~257 nm was observed. This authenticates the size variation of CuO nanoparticles obtained from different concentrations of β -CD. This phenomenon was also authenticated from the DLS measurements. The DLS measurement helps us to know the hydrodynamic radii of the particles produced from two different concentrations of β -CD (1 mM and 10 mM). Table 1 shows the absorption maximum and hydrodynamic radii of the CuO particles produced from different concentrations of β -CD solutions.

From the UV-Visible absorption spectra, we conclude that the CuO particles are formed from aqueous solutions of CDs in alkaline pH ~10-12. Finally particles of different size were also obtained from variable concentrations of β -CD.

Fig. 6. Absorption spectra of CuO nanoboxes obtained from α -, β - and γ -CD solutions (a) and plot of $(\alpha E_p)^2$ vs E_p for direct transition of CuO nanoboxes (b). Conditions : [CD] = 0.0396 g in 5 ml water, $[CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O/CuCl_2/Cu(OAC)_2] = 0.1$ M and $[NaOH] = 1.0$ M.

Fig. 7. (A) UV-Vis spectra for (a) 4-NP and (b,c) successive reduction of 4-NP catalyzed by CuO nanoparticles at intervals of 30 s. (B) Absorbance vs time (s) plot for the reduction of 4-NP in presence of CuO particles. (C) UV-Vis spectra for CuO nanoparticles with the addition of borohydride. Conditions : [4-NP] = 0.1 mM; [NaBH₄] = 0.1 M; [CuO] = 0.001 M.

Table 1. Wavelength of maximum absorption and hydrodynamic radii of the CuO particles produced from different concentrations of β-CD solutions

Serial no.	Concentration (mM)	Absorption maximum (nm)	Hydrodynamic radii (nm)
1.	1	279	153
2.	3	275	128
3.	10	255	78

Growth mechanism of CuO nanoboxes :

Here, we proposed the growth mechanism for the formation of box shaped CuO nanoparticles. It is known that the crystallographic structure of the nuclei and seeds, during the nucleation process and their subsequent growth stage, are the key parameters in influencing the final shapes of the nanocrystals. Similar to the formation of nanocubes and nanooctahedrons, the CuO nanoboxes must have evolved from single crystalline seeds. The almost

exclusive appearance of box shaped nanocrystals suggests the predominant formation of single crystal particles from the nucleation process. A single absorption band centered at $\lambda_{max} \sim 278$ nm is observed in this spectrum (Fig. 6a). The optical absorption spectrum of the CuO nanostructures remains unchanged when the CuO nanoseed particles are subjected to a long growth period (3 h). This authenticates that the development of box shaped particles originates from the same. The prepared CuO samples become box shaped may be due to the selective capping of the crystal planes of CuO which becomes evident from the fringe spacing study. The interplanar spacing of these lattice fringe patterns is calculated to be 2.8 and 2.4 Å (Fig. 3d). These values correspond well with the spacing calculated for (110) and (11-1) crystallographic planes for monoclinic CuO (cell constants $a = 4.6837$ Å, $b = 3.4226$ Å, $c = 5.1288$ Å, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 99.54^\circ$ and $\gamma = 90^\circ$ (JCPDS 80-1916)).

Therefore, the growth mechanism takes place through (110) and (11-1) planes. It is seen that the lattice planes of the depicted particles are almost perfectly aligned, and an interesting and attractive phenomenon is that the lattice is not straightly aligned but with an angle at the joints (Fig. 3d). This indicates unfinished rotation followed by oriented attachment. At the bonding interface of the particles there is some disorder. This type of disorder at the bonding interface is the direct consequence of the oriented attachment^{17,43,44}.

During the preparation of CuO nanoparticles, the following reactions might have occurred :

In this case, CD moiety plays an important role because it has the capability of capping the particle surface through oxygen atoms of its primary hydroxyl group, which can control the growth of the particles. The controlled growth arises from the nature of CD and also from the concentration. The CD capped nanoparticles are stable enough and could not grow into larger ones on keeping the solution for long time. It has been well established that nanoparticles binding with a high concentration of strong organic receptors, which controls the sizes of the primary particles strictly, can orient into 2D or 3D nanostructures, driven by the interactions between organic receptors instead of between the core particles themselves. Under this situation, nanoparticles are the building blocks, and organic receptors play the role of concrete^{45,46}. In this case, the reaction temperature plays an important role in the formation of highly monodispersed CuO nanoparticles. At a temperature below 90 °C the formation of CuO nanoparticles has not been observed. On the other hand, CuO particles were rapidly crystallized at temperature ~80–90 °C in about 20 min. There in the presence of CD agglomeration of CuO nanoparticles is prevented. Larger particles are evolved while a lower β -CD concentration was employed. The evolution of CuO becomes faster when the reaction

mixture was boiled above 100 °C. But this did not affect the shape, size and morphology of the evolved CuO particles when the concentrations of all the reagents remained unaltered. The role of pH i.e. the concentration of NaOH was important in this synthetic protocol. Below pH ~10 the formation of CuO nanoparticles does not take place. Higher alkaline medium helps the formation of Cu(OH)₂ and finally that cupric hydroxide decomposed upon heating at a milder temperature to our desired box shaped CuO nanoparticles.

Application in catalysis :

The synthesized CuO nanoparticles has been found to be an effective catalyst for the reduction of 4-NP. The catalytic reduction of 4-NP with NaBH₄ was spectrophotometrically monitored in the presence of CuO nanoparticles as catalyst in aqueous medium. An aqueous solution of 4-NP has a maximum absorption (λ_{max}) at 316 nm, as shown by trace a (Fig. 7A). It has been observed that, after immediate addition of freshly prepared ice-cold aqueous solution of NaBH₄, the peak due to 4-NP was red shifted from 316 to 399 nm. This peak was due to the formation of 4-nitrophenolate (NP⁻) ions in alkaline condition caused by the addition of NaBH₄. The peak of nitrophenolate ion remains unaltered without addition of any catalyst though the reduction potential value of NP⁻/AP was higher than BO₃⁻/BH₄⁻ system. Addition of the catalyst caused diminution of the peak at 399 nm and a new peak successively increases at 294 nm which indicates the formation of the corresponding 4-amino phenol. The yellow color of the reaction mixture faded away and finally the solution becomes completely colorless. It is interesting to mention that after the quantitative reduction of 4-NP in the solution, a fresh aliquot of 4-NP has been found to be reduced again without the need of the addition of catalyst particles and NaBH₄. However, introduction of NaBH₄ was necessary while five such batches of 4-NP were introduced in the step wise fashion one after the other. Otherwise, the reaction slowed down and pseudo-first order reaction condition with respect to NaBH₄ could not be maintained. Here the catalyst remained active through out. In the reaction mixture, the concentration of NaBH₄ is large (~100 fold)

excess as compared to that of 4-NP, so that the second order reaction under the test can be treated as pseudo-first order one⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. Fig. 7B also justifies the pseudo-first order reaction strategy. From the decay curve of the absorbance at 399 nm, apparent rate constant k was determined. The evolved CuO nanoparticles remained unaltered even when CuO in solution (in absence of 4-NP) was individually treated with excess NaBH_4 which is shown by UV-Visible spectra (Fig. 7C). The presence of CuO nanoparticles drives the reaction favourably at a faster rate. Now it is well known that the catalytic activity of a particle depends critically on the size and shape. It can be seen from the FESEM and TEM images that the average particle sizes were ~ 100 nm and box shaped. Here box shaped CuO nanoparticle surface helps the electron relay from BH_4^- to 4-NP⁻ ions. Hence we observe color fading from the reduction reaction.

Conclusion :

In summary, we have demonstrated a simple, straight forward and cost effective way for the synthesis of CuO nanoboxes in gram level in aqueous phases via a green chemistry approach. The total reaction can be finished within ~ 20 min. The average size of the resultant CuO nanoboxes was about 100 nm. The optical absorption band gap CuO nanoparticles is determined to be 3.05 eV. The single crystalline nature of CuO nanoboxes was authenticated from XRD and SAED studies. The result shows that the formation of single crystalline CuO nanoparticles from any common precursors and the particle sizes of the CuO nanoparticles were varied simply by varying the concentration of β -CD. Finally, the synthesized CuO nanoparticle has been found to an efficient catalyst for 4-nitrophenol reduction.

Experimental

Reagents and instruments :

All the reagents were of AR grade. Double distilled water was used throughout the course of the reaction. Copper salts (sulfate, chloride and acetate), NaOH, 4-nitrophenol and NaBH_4 were purchased from Sisco Research Laboratory. α -, β - and γ -CD from Sigma-Aldrich and were used as received.

All absorption spectra were recorded in a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer (Kyoto, Japan) taking the solutions in a 1 cm quartz cuvette. DLS studies were measured with Malvern Nano ZS Zetasizer. FTIR spectral characteristics of the samples were collected in reflectance mode with Nexus 870 Thermo-Nicolet instrument coupled with a Thermo-Nicolet Continuum FTIR microscope. One drop of the test solution was placed on a KBr pellet and was dried under vacuum for 6 h before analysis. XRD analysis was performed with powder sample using a X-ray diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). XPS analysis was performed on an ESCA LAB MK II using Mg as the exciting source. The samples were prepared by placing one drop of the prepared nanoparticle suspension onto a clean glass slide and then allowing them to dry in air. The particle size, shape, and morphology of nanoparticles were observed with a field emission scanning electron microscope (Supra 40, Carl ZEISS Pvt. Ltd.). TEM, HRTEM and EDAX measurements of the metal sols were performed in a Hitachi H-9000 NAR instrument on samples prepared by placing a drop of fresh metal sols on copper grids precoated with carbon films, followed by solvent evaporation under vacuum. Raman spectra of CuO nanoparticles was obtained with a Renishaw Raman Microscope, equipped with a He-Ne laser excitation source emitting at a wavelength of 633 nm, and a Peltier cooled ($-70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) charge coupled device (CCD) camera. A Leica microscope with 20 \times objective lens was used. The holographic grating with 1800 grooves/mm and the 1 cm^{-1} slit enabled the spectral resolution. Laser power at the sample was 12 mW and the data acquisition time was 30 s.

Synthesis of CuO nanoparticles :

The box shaped CuO particles in the nano regime were synthesized in one step employing any one (α -, β - or γ -) of the cyclodextrins (CDs) in aqueous solution. After dissolving 0.396 g CD in water, 0.25 mL of 0.1 M of copper salt solution was mixed with it. After 2 min, 0.1 mL of NaOH (1.0 M) was introduced into the mixture so that, the pH of the solution becomes ~ 10 –12. The blue reaction mixture was shaken well and heated on a water bath at ~ 80 – $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After ~ 20 min, the solution turned

blackish yellow indicating the formation of CuO nanoparticles in the solution. Now the reaction mixture was centrifuged to obtain the black product. Finally, the black mass was washed with water and dried under vacuum. The percent yield was 93%. Variable concentration of β -CD (1 to 10 mM) and NaOH (0.01 to 0.04 M) were used to study the mechanism of formation of CuO nanoparticles.

Catalytic reaction :

In a typical reaction, 0.005 mL of 5×10^{-3} M aqueous suspension of the catalyst was taken along with an aqueous solution of 4-nitrophenol (0.03 mL of 10^{-2} M) in a 1 cm quartz cuvette and the volume of the solution was made up to 3 mL. Next, 0.3 mL of 0.1 M aqueous NaBH₄ solution was added to the reaction mixture and time-dependent absorption spectra were recorded in the UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 30 ± 2 °C.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the UGC, DST, NST and CSIR, New Delhi, and the IIT Kharagpur, for financial assistance.

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Pande *et al.* : Controlled synthesis of CuO box shaped nanoparticles and their application in nitrophenol reduction

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